

MODERN APPROACH METHODS TO THE PROCESS OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION AND TRAINING

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Annotation

This article examines the possibilities in the cluster approach of teaching English to preschool children.

Annotatsiya

Maqolada maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarga xorijiy til o'rgatishda klaster yondashuvidan foydalanish xususida so'z yuritiladi.

Аннотация

В данной статье рассматривается возможности в кластерный подход обучение английский язык детей дошкольного возраста.

One of the modern types of organization of the educational process are educational clusters. However, before talking about the cluster in education, you need to understand the basic concept. Cluster represents a combination of several homogeneous elements that can be considered as independent units with certain properties. This the method is logical because it helps to work with a large amount of data it needs to be studied, the main thing is to systematize and it is necessary to present him in a certain way. It can be used for introductory or advertising stage of the subject to systematize existing information and identifying areas of insufficient information. The mental activity of preschool children is fading in the cluster: ask questions, highlight the main thing, compare, build cause-and-effect connections and develop the ability to draw conclusions. The cluster method can be used in the course of educational activities in the study of various items in English. When using this method, the work form can be individual, group and team. It is defined in depending on the goals and objectives, the capabilities of the teacher and the children's team. You can transfer one form to another. With new knowledge, based on personal drawings and taking into account the knowledge gained, a general graphic scheme in the form of a joint discussion of the material covered. Cluster the technique develops systemic thinking, teaches children to systematize not only educational material, but also its value of judgment, teaches children to formulate and express your thoughts in English, based on

observations, experience and new knowledge, develops the ability to simultaneously consider several positions, creatively process information. Educational activities with using the cluster method allows preschoolers to express themselves, express your vision of the problem and freedom of creative activity. Generally, non-traditional technologies used in the educational process enhance motivate children, create an atmosphere of cooperation and increase self-esteem children, give them a sense of creative freedom. success in education and education can only be achieved if it is interesting for children. Therefore, the educator must constantly look for new methods of education and learning, be able to apply them in practice, accumulate and apply everything that can transform activity into joyful knowledge. Just how much changes in his pedagogical activity will quickly occur, the goal depends activities of the teacher of the English language, aimed at finding, mastering and introduction of educational innovations. Teachers are currently facing global challenges: ensuring an individual way of development of the child through the use of all types of activities stipulated by state standards educational, individual, constructive research, organizational and design. Teachers need to find new pedagogical technologies in the organization of correctional and educational the process of forming a personality with a communicative competence. The child should be independent and focused on relationships in various activities - play, communication, cognitive research, projects, etc. A preschool child knows how to ask questions to adults and peers, show interested and interested in them interaction, tries to independently explain the phenomena of nature and people's actions; prone to observation, experimentation. In the process of learning preschoolers, the educator makes his personal contribution to joint activities in the assimilation of educational materials, sharing knowledge, ideas and methods of action. In addition, it takes place in an environment of good will and mutual support, which allows not only to acquire new knowledge, but and develop cognitive activity, turning it into higher forms cooperation. Because the game is an independent activity of children, in which the child's psyche manifests itself. This is a form of organizing the life of preschool children. age. It is one of the means of comprehensive education of children. This is the method and the way children are taught and raised. Play is a means of preparation children to educational activities.

Studies by famous scientists and educators have shown that thanks to integrated game management can influence children by the content of the game, its organization, structure, moral attitudes of children, level of development children's game. Children's play is diverse in its content, character and organizations. Creative games are invented by children on their own. there will be predefined rules. Thus, the role of preschool

educational institution in the pedagogical process is very large and the game widely used in the education and training of preschool children.

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